

MANUFACTURING ANALYSIS OF WET FILAMENT WOUND PIPES AND PRESSURE VESSELS.

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ABSTRACT

Manufacturing analysis of carbon/epoxy pipes and pressure vessels have been performed. Two thick walled filament wound pipes have been produced. Ciba-Geigy LY556/HY917/DY070 epoxy resin and Toray T700S carbon fibre was used. Mandrel material was aluminium. Strains and temperatures during winding and curing have been measured. Fibre content have been measured on the completed pipes. The developed process model has been used to calculate the measured parameters. General agreement is good. The software has been used to calculate residual stresses in the cylindrical shell of a pressure vessel. Material, geometry and process are similar to those used for the pipes. Some process parameters affecting the residual stress state are identified. Initial roving tension, stacking sequence and working temperature are varied. The results indicate that the stacking sequence affects the tangential stress on the inner radius of the composite.

KEYWORDS: Filament Winding; Processing; Carbon Fibre; Residual Stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerical simulations and measurements are important in order to gain a better understanding of the complex filament winding process and thereby being able to optimize the processing conditions. Extensive research has been performed in this area during the last ten years [1-5]. Some of the research has however been performed on prepreg winding. In this paper has a new process model restricted to wet filament winding of thick walled cylinders with a thermoset resin been used[6]. The software is available at SICOMP.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL

2.1 General assumptions

Resins commonly used in wet filament winding have low viscosity during the winding stage because a good impregnation is needed. Measurements performed by Cai [4] and at SICOMP indicate that the resin pressure normally is low during wet filament winding. The resin pressure is assumed to be zero in this process model. The influence of the resin flow on the stress-strain state in the structure is hence neglected and no flow calculation is included in the model. The effects of void content are also neglected. Rigid connection between mandrel and composite is assumed at the cylinder ends. No effect from resin shrinkage is included in the calculations in this paper.

2.2 Material model

The achieved fibre content distribution is calculated. Resin material data is assumed to be a function of degree of cure, temperature and material state. A micro-mechanical model is used to update laminae data throughout the process.

3. MATERIAL DATA

Carbon fibre Toray T700S with Tex 800 and the Ciba-Geigy LY556 /HY917 /DY070 epoxy resin have been used for all experiments. Many of the used fibre data are nonaccurate handbook values. Material data and reaction kinetics data for the used epoxy can be found in [6]. Compaction model and compaction data from [5] have been used.

Table 1. Used material data for carbon fibre T700S.

Longitudinal Elastic Modulus (MPa)	230000
Transverse Elastic Modulus (MPa) *	13800
Longitudinal Shear Modulus (MPa) *	8960
Transverse Shear Modulus (MPa) *	4830
Longitudinal Poissons Ratio (-) *	0.2
Longitudinal Thermal Expansion Coeff.(1/°C) *	-0.7·10 ⁻⁶
Transverse Thermal Expansion Coeff. (1/°C) *	10.1·10 ⁻⁶
Density (kg/m ³)	1800
Specific Heat (J/kg°C)	712
Transverse Thermal Conductivity (W/m°C) *	6.28
Fibre Volume Content at Zero Pressure (-) *	0.51
Fibre Volume Content at Infinite Pressure (-) *	0.829
Compaction Spring Constant (N/m ²) *	158.6

* Fibre data taken from other carbon fibres than T700S.

4. MEASUREMENTS

Windings have been performed on a 4-axis, numerically controlled winding machine. An aluminium mandrel equipped with axial and tangential strain gages and a temperature sensor on the inner surface have been used. The pipes were wound with a resin temperature of 40 °C but with mandrel and fibre at room temperature. A temperature sensor was placed in the middle of the composite wall thickness during winding. After completed winding the pipe was put into a convection oven. The air temperature in the oven was increased with a rate of 2 °C/min. After completed curing the circulation fan was stopped and the oven allowed to cool.

5. PROCESS PARAMETERS

Table 2. Process parameters for the pipes.

PARAMETERS	PIPE 120	PIPE 124
Layup (mm, °)	10.1, ± 89.5	3.2, ±33 + 3.2, ±89.5 + 3.2, ±35
Layer Thickness (mm)	0.24	0.27
Mandrel Dimensions (mm)	Ø _i =140, Ø _o =150	Ø _i =140, Ø _o =150
Roving Tension (mm,MPa)	10.1, 28	3.2, 27 + 3.2, 28 + 3.2, 31
Cure Cycle (h,°C)	6, 80 + 3, 140	6, 80 + 3, 140

Initial roving tension is defined as the effective fibre tension measured at the winding eye.

6. PIPE 120

6.1 Temperature

A constant heat transfer coefficient of $27 \text{ W/m}^2\text{°C}$ for the convection oven has been used in the calculations. The temperature difference between the mandrel and the composite is generally less than 2 °C . The temperature increase due to generated heat from the epoxy during curing is some 3 °C . Gelation occurs when the material temperature has reached 80 °C at 490 minutes process time.

Figure 1. Measured and calculated temperature in mandrel and middle of composite for Pipe 120.

6.2 Cure

Gelation occurs at 17 % degree of cure for this epoxy. The degree of cure would reach a limit value of 75 % at 80 °C if the temperature was not increased. Full cure is reached when the material temperature is 140 °C .

Figure 2. Calculated degree of cure in middle of composite for Pipe 120.

6.3 Fibre content

Pieces were cut at different radial positions and with different radial thickness from the pipe after manufacturing. They were burned in an oven at 450 °C together with a reference piece of carbon fibre. Weight analysis was used to calculate the fibre volume content with compensation for a small weight loss of the carbon fibre and an assumed void content of 3 %. Mean values from three samples were used. The values are from samples with radial thickness of 3 mm, 5.05 mm and 10.1 mm. Agreement is good and indicates that a sharp increase of the fibre content on the inner radius of the pipe might exist.

Figure 3. Measured and calculated fibre volume content in composite for Pipe 120.

6.4 Strain

The strains are small after winding. Separation between mandrel and composite is calculated during cooling to room temperature at 1020 minutes process time. General agreement is good.

Figure 4. Measured and calculated axial and tangential mechanical strain in mandrel for Pipe 120.

7. PIPE 124

Temperatures and degree of cure are similar to Pipe 120. The agreement in fibre content is a bit poorer than for Pipe 120. Pipe 124 has small strains after winding. A large deviation in the axial strain during thermal expansion to 80 °C before gelation can be observed. A possible explanation to this is that the connection between mandrel and composite at the cylinder ends is not rigid before gelation. Pins with small diameter were used in the experiments to enable turnaround of the axial winding angles. Separation between mandrel and composite is calculated during cooling to room temperature at 980 minutes process time.

Figure 5. Measured and calculated axial and tangential mechanical strain in mandrel for Pipe 124.

8. PRESSURE VESSEL

8.1 Process data

The residual stress state in a pressure vessel with the same material and geometry as the pipes has been calculated. Some checks on the predicted general residual stress state with this process model has previously been done on glass/epoxy pipes[7]. A similar layout to those commonly used in pressure vessels has been chosen for the calculations. Some process parameters has been varied to see how they affect the residual stress state. The cure cycle would also affect the stress state but this parameter has not been studied in this analysis. Separation between liner and composite during cooldown to 25 °C occurs according to the calculations. Pressure vessels with this material are also often internally pressurised to create plastic deformation in the liner and this procedure adds additional stresses that are not accounted for here.

Data : Aluminium liner with $\varnothing_1=140.4$ mm and $\varnothing_0=150$ mm. 0.25 mm wound layer thickness. Cure cycle is 6 h 80 °C + 3 h 140 °C.

Table 3. Process parameters for the pressure vessels.

PARAMETERS	VESSEL 1	VESSEL 2	VESSEL 3
Layup (mm,°)	3,±90+4,±15 + 3, ± 90	3,±90 + 4,± 15 + 3,± 90	2,± 15+ 3,± 90 +2,± 15+3,± 90
Roving Tension(mm,MPa)	10, 30	1.5,15+8.5,40	10, 30

8.2 Vessel 1

The calculated residual stress state has a radial tension stress lower than 2 MPa. Tension stresses transverse to the fibre direction are in the order of 15 MPa. A peak tension stress in the fibre direction at the inner radius of the composite has a value of 200 MPa.

Figure 6. Calculated residual stress state at 25 °C for Vessel 1.

The temperature was increased to 100 °C after manufacturing to see how the working temperature affects the stress state. The main effect is that the stresses transverse to the fibre direction are changed from tension to compression..

Figure 7. Calculated residual stress state at 100 °C for Vessel 1.

8.3 Vessel 2

The overall effect of the varied initial roving tension seem to be small. Here it should be pointed out that the allowed tension range in this process often is some 15-40 MPa for carbon fibre. Extremely low roving tension is hard to get because of friction in the process. The upper tension limit is often defined by the processability of the fibre.

Figure 8. Calculated residual stress state at 25 °C for Vessel 2.

8.4 Vessel 3

The stress distribution is generally smoother. The tangential stress peak on the inner radius of the composite has disappeared. This might be good since the internal pressure in the vessel creates tension stresses in the structure during usage. Further analysis of the calculations show that the stress peak was created from interaction between liner and composite. When the structure is heated to 80 °C the liner expands and stretches a thin layer of the carbon fibre in Vessel 1. The tangential stress is local due to the very low radial elastic modulus of the composite before gelation. This tangential fibre stress is locked into the composite when the epoxy cures. The stress peak disappears with the layup in Vessel 3 because it has a very low tangential modulus before gelation on the inner radius of the composite.

Figure 9. Calculated residual stress state at 25 °C for Vessel 3.

9. CONCLUSION

The process model gives good agreement with measurements from the pipes. The calculations of the residual stress state on the pressure vessels indicate relatively low stresses. Tension stresses transverse to the fibre direction in the order of 15 MPa are however calculated. A 200 MPa tensional stress peak in the fibre direction at the inner radius of the composite can be eliminated by a change of the layup.

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TRANSFER MOULDING

